

IMPROVEMENT OF THE METHODOLOGY FOR MEASURING THE VOLUMETRIC ACTIVITY OF RADON IN AIR, WATER, AND SOIL

G.M. Akhmedov¹, P.M. Matyakubova²

Doctoral student at TSTU¹

Doctor of Technical Sciences, Professor at TSTU²

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15590243>

Abstract. *This article presents the developed methodology for measuring the volumetric activity of radon gas in air, water, and soil, as well as the results of its validation confirming the accuracy and reliability of the method.*

Keywords: *radon meter, measurement, air, water, soil, radon, volumetric activity, sample, environment.*

Introduction: Environmental pollution affects our lives in many ways. In this regard, the presence of radon gas in many locations depends on naturally formed geological features, and in areas with large deposits of minerals and rocks, the level of radon can be high [1]. Additionally, the amount of radon in air, water, soil, and building materials changes under the influence of external factors. The absence of a functioning standardized methodology for measuring radon in the Republic of Uzbekistan has long been a serious obstacle in assessing radiation safety [2].

An analysis of existing types of radon meters was carried out in the Republic, and a classification of radon meters was formed based on their names and performed functions, characteristics and design, operability, number of measured components, and the operation system of the semiconductor sensitive element. As a result of the analysis, the types of radon meters used in the Republic were Alpha GUARD, Alfarad Plus, and RAA-20P2 Alpha-radiometer. Measurement methodologies for Alpha GUARD, Alfarad Plus, and RAA-20P2 Alpha-radiometers were not defined in either the state language or other languages.

In 2021, scientists from the Institute of Physics and Technology of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan invented radon meters of the RR-4M type. For this radon meter, technical specifications, user manual, calibration methodology, and measurement methodology were presented; however, problems were identified in the assessment of error and uncertainty of measurement results.

Methods: During the research, the national standard O‘z MSt 402:2024 “Methodology for Measuring the Volumetric Activity of Radon in Air, Water, and Soil” was developed. The scope of application of this methodology covers the measurement of volumetric activity of radon in residential buildings, sanitary-epidemiological services, medical institutions with radon baths, construction organizations, organizations engaged in meteorological and seismic services for earthquake forecasting, as well as in public and industrial buildings [4].

In addition, the following measuring instruments were used in the course of the measurements:

Name and Type of Measuring Instruments	Metrological Characteristics of Measuring Instruments
--	---

Radonmeter “RR-4M”, “RR-5M”, “RR-6M”, and “RR-7M”	Measurement range: from 1 to 2000 Bq/m ³ Measurement error: ±15%
Scales Measuring tape	Measurement range: from 0 to 5 kg Measurement error: ±1 g
Volumeter	Included in the measuring instrument set
Stopwatch	Measurement range: from 0 to 30 minutes Measurement error: ±1 second
Measuring tape	From 0 to 5 m; Measurement error: ±1 cm

Instead of the above-mentioned measuring instruments, it is permitted to use other measuring and testing instruments with metrological characteristics not lower than theirs. Measurements were carried out under the following normal conditions:

Air temperature: from minus 5 to 35 °C

Relative humidity: (30 ÷ 80)%

Atmospheric pressure: (84 ÷ 106.7) kPa

According to O‘zMSt 402:2024, when measuring the volumetric activity of radon gas in water, the sampling vessel is completely filled with the water sample, the air outlets are hermetically sealed, and the sampling time (t_1) is recorded in the measurement protocol. This is considered a simple universal method and is suitable for the other aforementioned devices.

The measurement is carried out by determining the residual activity in the measuring chamber; radon gas from the water sample is purged into the measuring chamber by air flushing for 5 minutes, after which, upon mixing in the air system, the measurement start time t_2 is recorded in the protocol, and the volumetric activity of radon is measured.

The residual activity in the measuring chamber is measured using a radon meter, and the obtained value Q must be $Q \leq 20$ Bq/m³.

The measurement of radon activity is determined by the following formula:

$$Q_x = Q \cdot \left(1 + \frac{V_2}{V_1}\right) \cdot \exp(\lambda_{Rn} \cdot t) \quad (1)$$

The total measurement time does not exceed 20 minutes.

Using a radon meter, there are two methods for determining radon gas released from the soil surface:

Method 1: Radon gas samples are collected in a special chamber and then analyzed separately on the radon meter. The radon flux density Q_x is calculated by the following formula:

$$Q_x = Q \cdot \left(1 + \frac{V_2}{V_1}\right) \cdot \frac{(V_1 + V_3)}{T \cdot S} \cdot \exp(\lambda_{Rn} \cdot t) \quad (2)$$

Method 2: Radon is directly directed into the measuring chamber and analyzed on-site.

The chamber is held at a height of 50 cm, and the pump is turned on for 5 minutes. The residual radon in the chamber is measured (Q_0 must be ≤ 20 Bq/m³). The chamber is placed in the prepared location within 15 seconds, the pump operates for 5 minutes. After turning off the pump, direct measurement begins, which continues for 20 minutes.

$$Q_x = (Q - Q_\phi) \cdot \frac{(V_1 + V_3)}{T \cdot S_2} \quad (3)$$

When measuring the volumetric activity of radon gas in air or in collected (sampled) air, the analyzed air is directed into the measuring chamber, and the measurement is carried out for 20 minutes.

The formula for determining the volumetric activity of radon-222 in air samples collected in sampling vessels is:

$$Q_X = Q \cdot \left(1 + \frac{V_2}{V_1}\right) \cdot \exp(\lambda_{Rn} \cdot t) \quad (4)$$

here: V_2 — volume of the measuring chamber, V_2 (in liters);

V_1 — volume of the selected water sample, V_1 (in liters); t — time elapsed from the moment of water sampling to the start of measurements, minutes, $t=t_2-t_1$;

λ_{Rn} — decay constant of radon-222, min^{-1} , $\lambda=1.26 \times 10^{-4} \text{ min}^{-1}$

α — coefficient of radon solubility in water, $\alpha=0.25$

The change in the solubility coefficient depending on temperature within the temperature range specified in the radon meter operating instructions changes the calculation result by no more than 0.5% [4].

Results: In accordance with the national standard O‘z MSt 402:2024 “Methodology for measuring the volumetric activity of radon in air, water, and soil” and using the above-mentioned measuring instruments, the following results were obtained.

To confirm the reliability of the methodology for measuring the volumetric activity of radon in air, water, and soil, two employees conducted measurements of the volumetric activity of radon in the air sample shown below four times a day over a period of 4 days and obtained the results presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Results of measuring the volumetric activity of radon in air samples taken from water

№	Results of measurements								
	1- Employee				Bq/m ³	2- Employee			Bq/m ³
	1- day	2- day	3- day	4- day	1- day	2- day	3- day	4- day	
1	0,500	0,501	0,500	0,500	0,501	0,501	0,500	0,500	
2	0,500	0,501	0,500	0,500	0,501	0,501	0,501	0,500	
3	0,500	0,5	0,500	0,500	0,501	0,501	0,501	0,501	
4	0,500	0,5	0,500	0,500	0,501	0,501	0,501	0,501	

To confirm the reliability of the developed methodology for measuring the volumetric activity of radon in air, water, and soil, validation of this methodology was carried out, the results of which are presented in Table 2.

Table 2.

Results of the validation of the methodology for measuring the volumetric activity of radon in air, water, and soil

Names of calculated operational parameters	Results of calculations based on formulas of operational parameters
Precision	$T_1 = \sum n_i \bar{x}_i = 16.015$ $T_2 = \sum n_i \bar{x}_i^2 = 8,015$ $T_3 = \sum n_i = 32$ $T_4 = \sum n_i^2 = 128$ $T_5 = \sum (n_i - 1) * S_i^2 = 2,75E - 06$

Repeatability	$S_r = \sqrt{\frac{T_5}{T_3 - p}} = 0,0003$
Interlaboratory dispersion	$S_L^2 = \left[\frac{T_2 * T_3 - T_1^2}{T_3(p-1)} - S_r^2 \right] * \left[\frac{T_3(p-1)}{T_3^2 - T_4} \right] = 2,48813E-14$
Reproducibility	$S_R = \sqrt{S_r^2 + S_L^2} = 0,0003$
Repeatability limit	$r = 2\sqrt{2} \cdot S_r = 0.00096$
Reproducibility limit	$R = 2\sqrt{2} \cdot S_R = 0.00096$
Cochran's criterion (If the statistical value is less than or equal to its critical value at the 5% level, the tested item is considered valid)	<p>P=8 та Cкж=0.68</p> $C = \frac{S_{max}^2}{\sum_{i=1}^p S_i^2} = 0.35$
Grubbs' criterion (If the statistical value is less than or equal to its critical value at the 5% level, the tested item is considered valid)	<p>p=8 C_гp=2,126</p> $C = \frac{X_{max} - \bar{X}}{S} = 1,23$ $C = \frac{\bar{X} - X_{min}}{S} = 1,09$
Accuracy (bias)	$b = C_m - C_{REF} = 0,001$
Z criterion	<p>$Z \leq 2$ — the quality of the results is considered satisfactory;</p> <p>$2 < Z \leq 3$ — the quality of measurements is doubtful and requires additional verification;</p> <p>$Z > 3$ — the quality of measurements is considered unsatisfactory [5]</p> $Z = \frac{C_m - C_{REF}}{\delta} = 1,44$

Based on the obtained results, the Shewhart control chart appeared as follows:

Here: CL — central line; UCL — upper control limit; LCL — lower control limit [6].

Discussion: Considering the obtained results, since the statistical values according to Cochran's and Grubbs' criteria are less than the 5% critical value, the studied position is recognized as valid. According to the Z criterion, with $|Z| \leq 2$, the quality of the results is considered satisfactory. According to the Shewhart control chart, it can be seen that the result values do not exceed the established limits. This indicates the reliability and stability of the methodology for measuring the volumetric activity of radon in air, water, and soil.

Conclusion

It can be concluded that the obtained results satisfy the requirements of Cochran's and Grubbs' criteria, confirming the accuracy and reliability of the measurements. According to the Z criterion, the results possess high quality. Moreover, the developed methodology for using the instruments can serve as a basis for standardization and accreditation. This has made it possible to develop and validate a methodology for determining the volumetric activity of radon in air, water, and soil under the conditions of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The methodology developed based on the RR-4M instrument is operational and economically effective for practical application. This methodology can be widely applied in sanitary-epidemiological control, the construction industry, and seismic monitoring.

REFERENCES

1. Information from the World Health Organization website // Radon and its impact on human health. February 2, 2021. <https://www.who.int/ru/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/radon-and-health>.
2. Zh.E. Ruziyev, E.A. Ruziyev. "Analytical assessment of the mineral composition and radioactivity of underground drinking waters (based on the isotope Rn-222)" // Journal of Samarkand State University "Scientific Bulletin," 2019, No. 5.
3. ISO 13164-2:2013. Water quality — Radon-222 Part 2: Test method using gamma spectrometry.
4. O'zMSSt 402:2024 Volumetric activity of radon in air, water, and soil. Measurement method.
5. Guide to validation and verification of methods of the National Accreditation Center of the Republic of Uzbekistan O'ZAK.R-12.
6. ГООТ P 50779.42. Statistical methods. Shewhart control charts.